

Perceived Risk in Online Shopping

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Abstract

In the advent of e-commerce many issues have been faced in the development of online shopping. Consumer faces different risks in online shopping which decreases their interest to purchase products through various online shopping websites. This study shows about the customer perceived risk in online shopping. This study aims to examine risks in online such as functional risk, financial risk, time risk, social risk, physical risk, economic risk, after-sales risk and delivery risk. The network security of e-commerce must be strengthened. Customer should feel secure environment in online shopping. The study reveals that information risk, product risk and delivery risk have an intense effect on online purchase intention. Finally, it is important to strengthen integrity management in order to enable consumers to buy goods in online.

Keywords: Perceived Risk, Online Shopping, Behaviour, Purchase Intention

Introduction

Online shopping enables a customer to purchase goods or services from the seller by using internet through web browser. With the growth of online shopping new market coverage opportunities for stores can increase the demand and supply requirements. In the modern technology world people don't find time to go out and purchase products and services, online shopping provides a time space for customers to shop wide variety of goods and services in a single platform through various websites like flipkart, amazon, e-bay, snapdeal, myntra, club factory, first cry etc., these websites saves customer time and provides valid method of payment to complete the transaction. Once the payment has been accepted the goods and services are delivered in the either following ways like digital distribution, drop shipping, in store pick up, ticket codes and shipping.

Advantages

1. Convenience

Online stores are usually available 24 hours in a day and customers can buy through web sites at home or at work. In case of return of the product they doesn't need to visit the store. They can either claim for refund or return of the product.

2. Reviews of the product

Product information, safety procedures, manufacturer specifications are provided by online stores which gives advice, background information helps the customer to decide about the purchase of the product. Reviews are given by customers from all over the world.

3. Price and selection

Online shopping enables customers to enjoy unlimited deals provided by various vendors. shipping cost reduce the price advantage of online transaction. The retailer rapidly switch suppliers and vendors without disrupting users shopping experience.

Disadvantages

1. Fraud and security concern

Consumers face high risk of fraud than in face to face transaction. hackers broke into merchants website and steal customers information about their name, address and credit card number through the payment card industry. phishing enables the customers to feed their details into a system operated by malicious party.

2. Privacy

The shoppers face identity theft, defective products and the accumulation of spyware. customers information are easily available to the hackers who manipulates the system. customers are advised about the current technological scams and retailers offers shipping insurance in case of the product is lost or damaged.

Perceived Risk

Perceived risk is the key factor to consumer behaviour which influence the conversion of browsers into real buyers of the product. It is the amount of uncertainty perceived by the customers during purchase decision. The trust will be improved by increasing the transparency of the transaction process and illegal activities like password sniffing, data modification, spoofing and repudiation can be reduced. If the customer deals with dishonest merchants their information is stolen and it is advised to evaluate the vendor before going for online transaction.

Types of Perceived Risk

Research Methodology

The objective of this paper is to study about the consumer’s perceived risk in online transaction and the various eight factors perceived as a risk with the product/service to analyse the various threats associated and to identify the opinion and suggestion about the consumer perceived risk in online. The required sample size for this study is 200. These sample respondents are selected by systematic random sampling technique. The data analysis procedure is conducted through survey questionnaire method, responses are coded and data entered statistical package for social science

(SPSS). Factor analysis has been applied to examine the underlying dominant dimensions of risk in online shopping. Mean based ranking have been used to find out the online purchaser perception on threats considered as a risk in online shopping

Result Analysis And Discussion

Factor Analysis

Latent Dominant dimensions of Risk in Online Shopping

Each of the 26 factors influencing Risk in Online shopping are listed out in table.1 and respondent perceptions of those influencing factors are ascertained.

S.No	Factor Influencing Risk in Online shopping
1	Poor Quality of Product
2	Poor Performance
3	Inability to physically touch, sense or see product
4	Delay On Delivery
5	Time Consuming
6	Damaged Goods
7	Inability to reverse a transaction once the order has been Placed
8	Poor package
9	Product not worth financial price
10	High shipping cost
11	Net loss of money
12	Disapproval of the product by the family
13	Loss of status in consumer group
14	Misunderstanding due to the absence of human
15	Affect the image of people around me
16	Difficult to find right product
17	Inconvenience during online transaction
18	Waste of time
19	Online shopping makes irritable to return or repair the product
20	Prolonged online shopping causes adverse health effects
21	Buying counterfeit products can damage my health
22	Online payment services will charge an additional fee
23	Online shopping may cost more than the store
24	Delivery service will be charged with additional fee
25	Difficult to solve commercial disputes in online shopping
26	Products purchased online may miss after-sales service guarantee

The factor Analysis has been applied to table 1 to understand the underlying dominant dimensions of 26 Risk in online shopping variables and reduce them into a limited number of manageable and independent factors. The Principal Component Analysis of Extraction model and Rotation method of Varimax with Kaiser Normalisation have been used in the factor analysis and the results are shown in the table 2. to 5

Table 2 Descriptive statistics on Risk in Online Shopping

S.No	Factor Influencing Risk in Online shopping	N	Mean	Std.Deviation
1	Poor Quality	200	3.87	1.179
2	Poor Performance	200	3.82	1.256
3	Inability to physically touch, sense or see	200	3.37	1.440
4	Delay On Delivery	200	3.24	1.501
5	Time Consuming	200	3.85	1.139
6	Damaged Goods	200	3.37	1.339
7	Inability to reverse a transaction	200	3.65	1.272
8	Poor package	200	4.25	0.554
9	Product not worth financial price	200	4.29	0.527
10	High shipping cost	200	4.35	0.608
11	Net loss of money	200	4.30	0.602
12	Disapproval of the product	200	4.21	0.647
13	Loss of status in consumer group	200	4.10	0.657
14	Misunderstanding due to the absence of human	200	4.11	0.712
15	Affect the image of people around me	200	4.09	0.681
16	Difficult to find right product	200	4.08	0.665
17	Inconvenience during online transaction	200	4.13	0.665
18	Waste of time	200	4.13	0.626
19	Irritable to return or repair the product	200	4.17	0.673
20	Causes adverse health effects	200	4.09	0.659
21	Counterfeit products can damage my health	200	4.10	0.677
22	Online payment services will charge an additional fee	200	4.10	0.673
23	Cost more than the store	200	4.17	0.627
24	Delivery service charged with additional fee	200	4.17	0.556
25	Difficult to solve commercial disputes	200	4.30	0.593
26	Product miss after-sales service guarantee	200	4.36	0.549

The table 2 shows that with lower standard deviation values, the mean values of Risk in online shopping variables are the robust measures of them.

Table 3 Communalities and MSA of Risk in Online Shopping

S.No	Factor Influencing Risk in Online shopping	Communalities	MSA
1	Poor Quality	0.660	0.470
2	Poor Performance	0.519	0.374
3	Inability to physically touch, sense or see	0.618	0.461
4	Delay On Delivery	0.535	0.487
5	Time Consuming	0.638	0.374
6	Damaged Goods	0.479	0.499
7	Inability to reverse a transaction	0.596	0.513

8	Poor package	0.624	0.449
9	Product not worth financial price	0.712	0.454
10	High shipping cost	0.733	0.428
11	Net loss of money	0.666	0.495
12	Disapproval of the product	0.644	0.507
13	Loss of status in consumer group	0.574	0.501
14	Misunderstanding due to the absence of human	0.570	0.439
15	Affect the image of people around me	0.593	0.500
16	Difficult to find right product	0.530	0.457
17	Inconvenience during online transaction	0.523	0.413
18	Waste of time	0.691	0.376
19	Irritable to return or repair the product	0.667	0.394
20	Causes adverse health effects	0.530	0.535
21	Counterfeit products can damage my health	0.558	0.439
22	Online payment services will charge an additional fee	0.653	0.466
23	Cost more than the store	0.691	0.405
24	Delivery service charged with additional fee	0.606	0.473
25	Difficult to solve commercial disputes	0.565	0.471
26	Product miss after-sales service guarantee	0.623	0.412

The table 3 reveals that Risk in online shopping variables have Communalities ranging from 0.479 to 0.733 and MSA values ranging from 0.374 to 0.535. Therefore, those Risk in online shopping variables are fit for factorization.

Table 4 KMO and Bartlett’s Test for Factorization of Risk in online shopping

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy	0.451
Barlett’s Test of Sphericity Approx. Chi-Square	511.517
Df	325
P-Value	0.000

The Table 4 shows that KMO-MSA test and Barlett’s Test of Sphericity indicates that factor analysis can be applied to 26 Risk in online shopping variables.

Table 5 Variance Explained by Risk in online shopping variables

Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings			
Component	Eigen Values	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	1.892	7.278	7.278
2	1.728	6.646	13.923
3	1.687	6.487	20.411
4	1.59	6.114	26.524
5	1.535	5.904	32.428
6	1.449	5.575	38.003

7	1.331	5.119	43.122
8	1.257	4.833	47.956
9	1.163	4.473	52.429
10	1.125	4.327	56.756
11	1.044	4.016	60.772

Table 6 Factor Loading of Risk in online shopping

Factors	Variables	Factor Loading
Factor 1	Affect the image of people around me	0.706
	Misunderstanding due to the absence of human	0.583
Social factor (SF)	Loss of status in consumer group	0.480
	Disapproval of the product	0.444
Factor 2 Economic factor (EF)	Difficult to solve commercial disputes	0.689
	Online payment services will charge an additional fee	0.665
Factor 3 Opportunity factor (OF)	Inconvenience during online transaction	0.693
	Difficult to find right product	0.501
Factor 4 Quality factor (QF)	Poor Quality	0.729
	Poor package	0.594
	Inability to reverse a transaction	0.415
Factor 5 Delivery factor (DF)	Damaged Goods	0.669
	Cost more than the store	0.489
	Delay On Delivery	0.463
Factor 6 After-sales factor (AF)	Irritable to return or repair the product	0.803
Factor 7 Financial factor (FF)	Net loss of money	0.726
	High shipping cost	0.718
Factor 8 Health factor (HF)	Product not worth financial price	0.817
	Causes adverse health effects	0.438
Factor 9 Product factor (PF)	Inability to physically touch, sense or see	0.682
	Delivery service charged with additional fee	0.603
	Product miss after-sales service guarantee	0.467
Factor 10 Functional factor (FF)	Time Consuming	0.739
	Counterfeit products can damage my health	0.497
Factor 11 Time factor (TF)	Poor Performance	0.674
	Waste of time	0.640

Table 5 and 6 show 11 independent RIONS factors have been extracted out of 26 RIONS variables and they all together explain 60.772% of variance in them

The most dominant factor 1 explains 7.278 % of variance in RIONS variables and it is made of four RIONS variables of Affect the image of people around me, Misunderstanding due to the absence of human, Loss of status in consumer group, Disapproval of the product in the order of importance of their relative correlation with it and therefore, it has been labeled as Social factor.

The second most dominant factor 2 explains 6.46% of variance in RIONS variables and it is made of two RIONS variables of Difficult to solve commercial disputes and Online payment services will charge an additional fee, in the order of importance of their relative correlation with it and therefore, it has been named as Economic factor (EF).

The next dominant factor 3 explains 6.487% of variance in RIONS variables and it is made of two RIONS variables of Inconvenience during online transaction and Difficult to find right production, in the order of importance of their relative correlation with it and therefore, it has been named as Opportunity factor (OF).

The next dominant factor 4 explains 6.114% of variance in RIONS variables and it is made of three RIONS variables of Poor Quality, Poor package, Inability to reverse a transaction, in the order of importance of their relative correlation with it and therefore, it has been named as Quality factor (QF).

The next dominant factor 5 explains 5.904% of variance in RIONS variables and it is made of three RIONS variables of Damaged Goods, Cost more than the store and Delay On Delivery, in the order of importance of their relative correlation with it and therefore, it has been named as Delivery factor (DF).

The next dominant factor 6 explains 5.375% of variance in RIONS variables and it is made of one RIONS variable of Irritable to return or repair the product and it has been named as After-sales factor.

The next dominant factor 7 explains 5.119 % of variance in RIONS variables and it is made of two RIONS variables of Net loss of money and High shipping cost, in the order of importance of their relative correlation with it and therefore, it has been named as Financial factor (FF).

The next dominant factor 8 explains 4.833% of variance in RIONS variables and it is made of two RIONS variables of Product not worth financial price and Causes adverse health effects, in the order of importance of their relative correlation with it and therefore, it has been named as Health factor (HF).

The next dominant factor 9 explains 4.473% of variance in RIONS variables and it is made of three RIONS variables of Inability to physically touch, sense or see, Delivery service charged with additional fee and Product miss after-sales service guarantee, in the order of importance of their relative correlation with it and therefore, it has been named as Product factor (PF).

The next dominant factor 10 explains 4.327 % of variance in RIONS variables and it is made of two RIONS variables of Time Consuming and Counterfeit products can damage my health, in the order of importance of their relative correlation with it and therefore, it has been named as Functional factor (FF).

The last dominant factor 11 explains 4.016% of variance in RIONS variables and it is made of two RIONS variables of Poor Performance and Waste of time, in the order of importance of their relative correlation with it and therefore, it has been named as Time factor (TF).

Mean Based Ranking

Online purchaser perception on threats considered as a risk in online shopping

The threats considered as a risk in online shopping by respondent are listed below

S.No	Threats considered as a risk
1	E-mail address may be abused by others
2	Phone number may be abused by others

3	Personal information may be disclosed to other companies
4	Stealing credit card number
5	Digital Signature
6	Data Integrity

6 threats considered as a risk in online shopping at by respondent with their relative importance based on mean values are given in table.

Table 7

S.No	Threats considered as a risk	N	Mean	Rank
1	E-mail address may be abused by others	200	4.19	3
2	Phone number may be abused by others	200	4.13	4
3	Personal information may be disclosed to other companies	200	4.21	2
4	Stealing credit card number	200	4.34	1
5	Digital Signature	200	3.83	5
6	Data Integrity	200	3.77	6

Table 7 shows Stealing credit card number is the most important risk in online shopping at followed by Personal information may be disclosed to other companies.

Conclusion

From the perspective of a consumer's perceived risk, the consumer is willing to purchase product/service from an online vendor that is perceived low risk, even if the consumer's perceived ease of use on e-Commerce is relatively low.

From the study we infer that consumers consider the risk related to the online transaction (i.e., privacy, security, non repudiation.) as one of the important factors when they purchase on the Internet. Thus, diminishing such risk is considerably important to online vendors. There are Eight Risk factors perceived by the respondents, who perceived the most risk with the financial aspects and time loss of online shopping. Finally we conclude that, thus the respondents perceiving less overall risk with online shopping.

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